

1 **A whole-genome sequencing study of an X-family tuberculosis outbreak focus on**
2 **transmission chain along 25 years**

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28 **Abstract:** Lineage 4/X-family of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is not very notorious, except for the
29 CDC1551 strain. One strain of this family, named Ara50, caused one of the largest tuberculosis
30 outbreaks of the Aragon region, Spain, during the 1990s and remained until 2018. These X-strains
31 are characterised by high transmissibility and by carrying a low copy number of IS6110 in their
32 genomes. Epidemiological data of the 61 patients consisted of inmates, HIV seropositives,
33 intravenous drug users and the homeless. The application of whole-genome sequencing (WGS) to
34 36 out of 61 isolates, selected by IS6110-RFLP, allowed to confirm 32 as recent transmissions. We
35 found 10 SNPs in genes considered as virulence factors, five of them specific of this strain. WGS
36 identified three sub-clusters (CLSs). The largest one, sub-CLS 1, included 10 cases. Seven of them
37 shared a SNP in the *mce3C* gene, considered a virulence factor gene. Sub-CLS 2 involved familiar
38 cases, and no link was known for sub-CLS 3. Finally, the strain showed efficacy in latency as a
39 confirmed epidemiological link was established between two cases, with 6 years of distance in their
40 diagnosis. This outbreak study combined epidemiological and molecular analyses in order to
41 elucidate tuberculosis transmission.

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Key words: tuberculosis; tuberculosis outbreak; X-family tuberculosis strain

DNA sequences and GenBank Accession numbers

Sequences of Case 2 (Ara50 type) (accession number [SAMN15501351](#)) and Case 36 (evolution of Ara50 strain with one more *IS6110* copy) (accession number [SAMN15501352](#)) have been uploaded to BioSample database. They are included in the BioProject PRJNA645275.

91 **Text**

92 **1. Introduction**

93 Whole-genome sequencing (WGS) is nowadays essential for studying infectious diseases from both
94 molecular and epidemiological points of view [1]. Tuberculosis (TB) is still an important cause of
95 death, especially in developing countries where other diseases, such as AIDS, play an important
96 role in the fatal result [2].

97 *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is a complex pathogen with a long incubation and latent period, which
98 makes the study of outbreaks and contact tracing difficult [3]. There are seven different lineages
99 (Ls) and one animal strain branch, all of them potentially causing the disease and with specific
100 characteristics [4]. L4 is the most extended globally [5], and its success has been associated with
101 having a high copy number of insertion sequence (IS) *6110* [6]. However, CDC1551 strain,
102 belonging to L4, L4.1.1.3/X-family, with only four copies of IS*6110* showed an unusually high rate
103 of transmission in a rural area of the United States (US) in 1995 [7].

104 Aragon (a region in northern Spain) has applied genotyping to all *M. tuberculosis* complex isolates
105 for surveillance purposes routinely since 2004. Studies were performed in Zaragoza for the periods
106 1993–1995 and 2001–2004 [8]. Combining all the genotypes available, we discovered five
107 outbreaks caused by an X-family strain, but just one, named Ara50, grouped more than 50 cases. It
108 was the largest outbreaks in the 1990s among our population; likewise, we could find the same
109 genotype ongoing to 2018. This strain was selected to be studied due its similarity with CDC1551, a
110 known well-transmitted strain [7] with low copy number of IS*6110*, its long persistence, and the
111 large number of cases it produced. We applied WGS in order to study the molecular characteristics
112 of this X strain and to elucidate its evolution along 25 years and its transmission chain, as other
113 authors have succeeded using this technique [9, 10, 11]. We were successful in finding out the
114 molecular characteristics of the strain and partially successful in identifying the transmission chain.

115 **2. Materials and Methods**

116 **2.1 Clinical samples and cases**

117 Systematic genotyping of all *M. tuberculosis* strains isolated in Aragon, coordinated by public
118 health services, has been carried out since 2004 up to now. These RFLP genotypes are included in
119 Bionumerics software v7.6 (Applied Maths, Kortrijk, Belgium), which allowed the comparison
120 among all the analysed patterns, including those from two previous population studies from the
121 periods 1993–1995 and 2001–2004 in Zaragoza.

122 The search for X-family genotypes belonging to isolates from the period 2004–2019, among more
123 than 6000 IS6110-RFLP and spoligotype patterns, was performed in the Bionumerics software.
124 Fifty-two patterns belonged to the X-family and some of them were grouped in five clusters. One of
125 them, named Ara50, which involved 27 isolates corresponding to 26 different cases.

126 The search for this Ara50 genotype in the two previous studies, carried out in an Aragon population,
127 allowed the discovery of 34 more isolates between the periods of 1993–1995 (27 cases) and 2001–
128 2003 (seven cases), with an IS6110-RFLP pattern compatible with the Ara50 X-family strain. A
129 total of 61 genotypes were selected as possible Ara50 isolates. Enough DNA stored at -80°C was
130 available for 36 of them, which could be analysed by WGS.

131 Epidemiological, clinical and microbiological data of the patients were collected and carefully
132 studied. All the data were anonymous in order to protect the identity of the patients.

133 **2.2 Standard molecular typing**

134 DNA of the isolates was obtained using the cetrimonium bromide method, as previously described
135 [12]. All DNA extractions were stored at -80°C until sequencing. All the isolates were genotyped by
136 standardised techniques, including IS6110-RFLP (all the isolates), spoligotyping (all the isolates
137 since 2001) and 24-MIRU-VNTR (one representative isolate), as previously described [13, 14, 15].
138 The genetic patterns obtained were stored and analysed by Bionumerics database software.
139 Spoligotypes were systematically revised against the SITVIT database ([www.pasteur-
140 guadeloupe.fr:8081/SITVIT_ONLINE](http://www.pasteur-guadeloupe.fr:8081/SITVIT_ONLINE)). Gilla Kaplan kindly provided CDC1551 strain, used for
141 IS6110-RFLP and Spoligotyping techniques.

142 **2.3 IonTorrent sequencing**

143 Thirty-six isolates with a similar RFLP pattern, considered as part of the Ara50 cluster, were
144 recovered and sequenced using IonTorrent technology. The library was prepared using the Ion
145 Xpress™ Plus Fragment Library Kit, following the manufacturer's instructions, and the sequencing
146 and analysis took place in the Ion S5™ XL System. Once the sequences were obtained, they were
147 mapped against the reference strains H37Rv (NC_000962.3) and CDC1551 (NC_002755.2) using
148 the Torrent Mapper TMAP version 5.12.27. Variants were called, excluding high variable regions
149 such as *ppe* and *pe_pgrs* genes, by the Torrent Variant Caller plugin. This allowed us to obtain a
150 bam file to use for the Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV) program.

151 **2.4 Lineage and family identification by WGS**

152 We used the SNP classification of Coll et al. [16], in which each MTB lineage and family is
153 associated with specific SNPs in different genomic regions. The SNPs that classified the studied
154 strain as L4.1.1.3 and X-family are described in the Results section.

155 **2.5 Bioinformatic tools for the study of the genomes**

156 The fastQ files of the sequences obtained were introduced and analysed in Bionumerics software.
157 The program mapped the sequences against the reference strains H37Rv and CDC1551, and
158 obtained the different SNPs among the genomes analysed. The analysis of SNPs allowed the
159 construction of a dendrogram using the UPGMA method. For greater accuracy, strict SNP filtering
160 that removed positions with at least one ambiguous or unreliable base, gaps (maximum frequency
161 1%), non-discriminatory positions and *ppe* and *pgrs* genes, was applied. It was also considered that
162 the retained SNP positions had a minimum 5x coverage and that the minimum distance between
163 SNPs was at least 12 base pairs (bp). To study the phylogeny of the isolates and their drug-
164 resistance profile, the IGV program and TubercuList website
165 (<http://genolist.pasteur.fr/TubercuList/>) were used. For the *IS6110* location, reads containing the
166 first 30 and the last 30 nucleotides of the *IS6110* were selected using BLAST, and they were
167 subsequently studied using TubercuList.

168 **2.6. Phylogenetic tree**

169 The SNPs of Ara50 and X-non Ara50 strains were extracted using SNIPPY tool. The consensus
170 sequenced obtained, among CDC1551 and H37Rv sequences, were aligned and the tree was
171 constructed using Parsnp tool. The tree was visualized using TreeView tool.

172 **2.7 Data availability:**

173 Sequences of Case 2 (Ara50 type) (accession number [SAMN15501351](#)) and Case 36 (evolution of
174 Ara50 strain with one more *IS6110* copy) (accession number [SAMN15501352](#)) have been uploaded
175 to BioSample database. They are included in the BioProject PRJNA645275.

176 **3 Results**

177 Based on the *IS6110*-RFLP (five bands), spoligotyping (octal code 067776777760771) and 24-
178 MIRU-VNTR (253244332434425153322743, ordered according their appearance in the genome)
179 patterns, we suspected 61 cases were affected by this X-family strain. Fifty-six of these isolates had
180 an identical RFLP pattern. The other five had a slightly different pattern with five bands (but not
181 exactly at the same position) or with six bands in case the strain could have evolved. The different
182 patterns selected can be observed in Fig 1A.

183 Thirty-six isolates of the 61 suspected cases had the required amount of DNA to apply the WGS
184 technique. Once the WGS analysis was done, we discerned that two of the isolates were Haarlem
185 strains, as they had the specific SNPs for this family [16], while another was an X-strain, but not
186 from the Ara50 outbreak, as it had more than 150 SNPs in comparison to the rest of the isolates.
187 One more isolate was excluded, as it was a cross-contamination. Finally, 32 isolates were included
188 in the genomic study.

189 **3.1 Genomic Ara50 strain characterisation**

190 **3.1.1 IS6110 analysis**

191 WGS allowed the location study of the five copies of IS6110 determined in the RFLP genotype of
192 the Ara50 strain, the additional IS6110 in Case 36 and in the outgroup strains (the two Haarlem and
193 the non-Ara50 X strains). The results are shown in Table 1. All the points are referred to the H37Rv
194 genome (NC_000962.3) or to the *M. bovis* genome (LT708304.1), in case the location was not
195 present in H37Rv. Four of these IS6110 were at the same location that the ones in CDC1551 strain.
196 Ara50 had an additional IS6110 in the DR region. The IS6110-RFLP and Spoligotyping patterns of
197 Ara50 and CDC1551 strains are shown in Fig 1B.

198 **3.1.2 SNP analysis**

199 According to the SNP classification established by Coll et al. [16], this strain belonged to lineage
200 4.1.1.3/X-family, as it has SNPs in positions 931123, 62657, 514245 and 4229087.

201 Regarding the genes associated with antimicrobial resistance, we found mutations in *katG* (point
202 2156096), *embB* (point 4249408), *gyrA* (points 7362, 7585 and 9304), *tlyA* (point 1917972) and
203 *fbiA* (point 3641091). Nevertheless, none of these polymorphisms was established as conferring
204 resistance, which is in agreement with the antibiotic test results obtained by the clinical laboratories.

205 This strain had 918 SNPs when compared to H37Rv genome (NC_000962.3). The comparison
206 against CDC1551 genome revealed 408 SNPs. Fifty-seven SNPs were considered specific to the
207 Ara50 strain, as we detected them in comparison to other sequenced strains we had from other
208 studies (including other X strains and a variety of lineages) (Table S1). A phylogeny was
209 constructed using CDC1551, Ara50 and the X non-Ara50 genomes using H37Rv as an outgroup
210 (Fig S1). X non-Ara50 genome is more closely related with CDC1551 than Ara50 strain.

211 The strain had non-synonymous SNPs in 10 genes considered virulence factors [17]: *mmaA4*, *mbtB*,
212 *mmpL7*, *sigH*, *ctpC*, *pks7*, *pks5*, *katG*, *fadE29* and *lpqH*. The first five were specific SNPs, while
213 the last four were also present in CDC1551 and in the non-Ara50 X strains. The mutation in *pks7*
214 was both present in Ara50 and non-Ara50 X strains.

215 **3.2 Epidemiological study of Ara50 outbreak**

216 This strain has remained for 25 years. The first cases were detected in 1993, when our records
217 started, maintaining the highest number of cases per year in the first three years studied (1993–
218 1995). Since 2001, when the records started again, the number of cases per year has diminished
219 substantially, with a punctual rise in 2006. After 3 years with no cases, 2015–2017, the strain
220 reappeared in 2018 with two more cases. No other case has appeared since then (Fig 2).

221 The epidemiological study was carried out on the 56 cases described in Fig 2. The majority of
222 affected patients were autochthonous with ages from 4 to 87, with those aged between 16 and 45
223 being the most affected. Considering just the known ones, we observed a 55.6% of HIV+ patients
224 and a 38.8% of intravenous drugs (ID) users or ex-users. Besides, 78.6% were smokers and more
225 than 25% reported high alcohol consumption. Thirty-two cases presented a positive sputum smear
226 result and, therefore, were potentially infectious. We also observed a high proportion of
227 dysfunctional family structure (50%). A summary of the risk factors can be found in Table 2. In
228 addition, in order to study a possible neighbourhood link, a map marking the addresses of the cases
229 was constructed (data not shown). Six of the cases lived outside the city, while the rest were
230 distributed in the different neighbourhoods in Zaragoza. Nine of the patients had been in prison,
231 during or after the TB diagnosis. Moreover, four cases had been in the methadone unit closely in
232 time. No other epidemiological links could be established using the epidemiological information
233 alone.

234 **3.3 Ara50 genomic study**

235 The SNP analysis showed genetic links between several isolates (Fig 3).

236 There was a sub-cluster (CLS), sub-CLS 1, that included 10 isolates (Cases 27, 32, 52, 3, 20, 29, 39,
237 38, 41 and 56) related by the SNPs in positions 2292579 and 2698983. Moreover, it was split by a
238 third SNP in position 2212353, which was shared in seven of these isolates (Cases 3, 20, 29, 39, 38,
239 41 and 56). Four of them (Cases 27, 32, 29 and 39) could be epidemiologically related for being
240 part of the methadone unit programme and two more cases for being in prison (Case 39 and 38). We
241 know this strain circulated through one of Aragon's penitentiaries, where Case 38 was imprisoned
242 in 2005. The epidemiological information from these 10 cases can be found in Table 3.

243 Another sub-CLS, sub-CLS 2, was identified using WGS. It was constituted by four cases (28, 45,
244 44 and 46). Case 28 was the index case of this sub-CLS. The other three were not diagnosed until 6
245 years later, sharing SNPs in positions 625157 and 4194065. Epidemiological information showed

246 that Cases 28 and 44 were father and son, respectively. A new SNP appeared in position 3632058 in
247 the isolates of the last three cases. No epidemiological link was found between Cases 44, 45 and 46.

248 Finally, a sub-CLS 3 consisting of two cases, Cases 22 and 37, was identified. No epidemiological
249 link was found between them; however, both isolates had the same genomic sequence, sharing two
250 SNPs in positions 1114864 and 1498542.

251 There were four genomes, belonging to the period 1993–1995, that did not show any SNPs, being
252 Case 2 the earliest (1993). We considered them the original sequence of the strain.

253 In Table 4, the SNP distances among the 32 analysed genomes can be found. It is assumed that, if
254 there are ≤ 12 SNPs between isolates, both are the same strain. If there are ≤ 5 SNPs between
255 isolates, there was a recent contact [11]. For 24 isolates, the number of SNPs was ≤ 5 with at least
256 one isolate. For seven isolates, the number of SNPs were ≥ 5 in all the cases but ≤ 12 SNPs with at
257 least one isolate.

258 Using the link classification of Lalor et al. [11], the only “confirmed epidemiological link” was the
259 one between Cases 28 and 44, known as being father and son. The cases in prison and attending the
260 methadone unit were considered a “probable epidemiological link”, as they spent time in the same
261 location but the timing was unknown. Finally, the rest of the cases had a “possible epidemiological
262 link” for sharing the same neighbourhood and social practises (those who were users of ID). The
263 genetic and possible epidemiological links are shown in Fig 4.

264 The study of the SNPs that were detected, which are detailed in the dendrogram, was also carried
265 out. The genes involved and the effect of the SNP in terms of synonymous and non-synonymous
266 mutations can be found in Table 5.

267 One non-synonymous SNP in position 2212353 was found within the *mce3C* gene, an ATP-binding
268 cassette transporter related to virulence. This SNP was detected in seven isolates of sub-CLS 1, but
269 a different clinical behaviour could not be determined. The other two non-synonymous SNPs shared
270 by sub-CLS 1 were detected within *Rv2047c* and *Rv2402* genes, both considered hypothetical
271 proteins.

272 The SNPs transmitted from Case 28 to Case 44 in sub-CLS 2 were within *fabH* and *ctpJ* genes,
273 which are involved in fatty acids biosynthesis and cation transport, respectively. The other SNP
274 probably generated in Case 44 and shared by the other two isolates of sub-CLS 2 was located in the
275 intergenic region *alkB:Rv3252c*.

276 The SNPs shared by isolates of sub-CLS 3 were in *Rv0998* gene, considered a hypothetical protein,
277 and *dinG* gene, an ATP-dependent helicase involved in DNA repair and replication.

278 4 Discussion

279 This study focused on an X-family strain, Ara50 Strain. X-family became **better known** when strain
280 CDC1551 produced an outbreak in 1995. Previous studies have described the great ability of L2 and
281 L4 for spreading globally and related that with the high copy number of *IS6110* they presented [6].
282 What is interesting about the X-family is that it has a low copy number of *IS6110*, specifically, our
283 X strain carried five copies, despite being L4, and demonstrated a high transmission capacity during
284 the 1990s. Simultaneously, it has had a great ability to persist, as it has circulated for at least 25
285 years. Ara50 strain produced the largest outbreak in Aragon for 1993-1995 period, and continued
286 being one of the largest during the rest of the study period, with almost 60 cases in total. For 1993-
287 1995, 46.6% of strains were in cluster [8], for 2001-2003, 52.5% of strains [8] and for 2004-2018,
288 56.1% (not published), being the majority of clusters formed by two or three cases.

289 The discrimination power of WGS has been largely demonstrated [18]. According to this, WGS has
290 been useful to distinguish between evolved and not related strains, which shared a non-identical but
291 similar genotype. In this work, we could confirm the evolution of one isolate as having ≤ 12 SNPs
292 when compared to the Ara50 type strain. In addition, it shared the five locations of the *IS6110* with
293 Ara50. Modifications in the RFLP pattern were observed before for strains belonging to the same
294 cluster [19, 20]. In contrast, three of these isolates were not related to the Ara50 outbreak. The study
295 of the *IS6110* confirmed it, as were the IS number and location, was different to the ones for Ara50.
296 It was surprising that the number of *IS6110* turned out to be higher than expected for the observed
297 RFLP pattern, although this was previously observed [21].

298 The SNP study of Ara50 revealed this strain was more closely related to CDC1551(408 SNPs) than
299 to H37Rv (918 SNPs), something expected as both were X family strains. In addition, the
300 phylogenetic tree (FigS1) showed that X non-Ara50 strain is more related with CDC1551 than
301 Ara50 strain, however a close common ancestor among these three strains seems likely. Ara50 had
302 10 virulence factor genes affected. At least five seem to be specific for the strain; therefore, it is
303 possible that the success of the strain was due, in part, to some of these SNPs.

304 Tracking the transmission chain in this outbreak was difficult, as multiple infectious foci co-existed
305 at the same time, and it has been demonstrated that identical sequences could derive from different
306 transmission events [10]. Different from another outbreak studied in our laboratory [22], which was
307 contextualised in household and school environments, this outbreak had a high proportion of
308 individuals with risk factors, such as ID users, alcoholics, prisoners, homelessness and prostitution.
309 These individuals have many possibilities to concur in more than one context, creating a suitable
310 ground for TB transmission. Moreover, in these environments, the treatment of TB is not usually

311 followed correctly, and some patients abandon it and suffer relapses. A remarkable fact is that we
312 had some cases with an earlier TB episode. It could be that some of them were relapses or maybe
313 re-infections with the same strain, as they continued frequenting the same circles and behaviours. It
314 is noteworthy that the strain did not evolve any resistance to anti-tuberculosis drugs despite this.

315 WGS allowed the identification of several sub-CLSs. Sub-CLS 1 was special because a SNP in
316 position 2212353, shared by seven out of the 10 isolates, subdivided the CLS. If epidemiological
317 data had been considered alone, we would have assumed that the four isolates in the methadone unit
318 transmitted the strain among them. Nevertheless, two of the isolates had this SNP, but the other two
319 did not. As this SNP has circulated since 1993 and the methadone unit coincidence was not until
320 2002–2003, it suggests a different origin, despite being in the same place and close in time.
321 However, the ability of WGS to infer the direction of transmission was not very high. We could
322 only determine the transmission route in sub-CLS 2 by combining both epidemiological and genetic
323 information, as the transmission is towards the accumulation of SNPs [23]. This is consistent with
324 the findings of other authors [3, 10, 11]. Inferring the direction of transmission for sub-CLS 3 was
325 not possible using the genomic information, since both sequences were identical. However, the fact
326 that one isolate was diagnosed in 1995 and the other in 2006 suggested that Case 22 became
327 infected first.

328 The study of the SNP distance between isolates revealed that most of them had 0–5 different SNPs,
329 indicating recent contact [11]. For several isolates, unique SNPs were identified, so the SNP
330 distance increased for more than 12 SNPs in some cases, despite belonging to the Ara50 cluster.
331 This could mean that the SNPs occurred in each isolate individually after the transmission, as can
332 be observed in the isolates from sub-CLS 1, or were produced during the *in vitro* steps, as we
333 observed when analysing the contaminated isolate in the laboratory, which was far from being
334 identical to its contaminating isolate, as they differed in seven SNPs (data not shown). It is
335 important to take into account that this strain has been circulating for more than 25 years, so the
336 evolution of the strain has been possible. The SNP dendrogram showed four identical sequences,
337 with no SNPs in relation to the cluster, so we considered them the genome type. Just one of these
338 isolates, Case 2, was from 1993, when our study began. On one hand, we thought that this case
339 could be a possible spreader case due to its epidemiological characteristics. He was a young man
340 who lived near some of the cases that appeared later, and he was an ID user, HIV+ and imprisoned
341 after the TB diagnosis. Besides, it can be observed that Case 2 had recent contact (≤ 5 SNPs) with
342 24 of the patients, including those in the methadone unit and those in prison. On the other hand, the
343 fact that the three characteristic SNPs present in sub-CLS 1 were already observed in 1993 suggests
344 that the strain was circulating some years before.

345 Among the transmitted SNPs, the one in *mce3C* gene in sub-CLS 1 caught our attention for being in
346 a virulence factor gene, so it could be related with the success of this variant. This gene is part of
347 the *mce3* operon [24], which encodes for homologous ATP-binding cassette transporters related to
348 virulence as knock-out strains for this operon were attenuated [25, 26]. Virulent *M. bovis* strains
349 lack *mce3* operon, nevertheless this fact has been related with evolutionary differences between *M.*
350 *tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*, as host range [27]. Recently, Yong Zhang et al. [28] have demonstrated
351 that MCE3C protein is located on the surface of the cell, promoting mycobacterial adherence to
352 macrophages and allowing their entry into them, becoming an important gene in the first steps of
353 infection. We know that seven of the sequenced isolates had this SNP, and there could be more
354 among those unsequenced isolates. This SNP could be conferring an advantage in the ability of the
355 strain to infect macrophages.

356 A limitation of the study is that there is a period without data (1996–2000); therefore, several cases
357 were missed, as well as the cases prior to 1993, as the isolates were not genotyped. Besides, DNA
358 was not available for all the isolates, so the WGS was not applied to all known cases. Some of these
359 cases could be a link we have lost. A major difficulty in the study of TB outbreaks is the latency
360 period. As a person can become infected but not develop the disease until years later [29], it is a
361 challenge to determine when the transmission occurs and who infected whom. This strain proved to
362 be successful in latency, as can be observed in sub-CLS 2. Case 28 developed the disease in 2002,
363 then potentially infected his son, who did not develop the disease until 2008.

364 **5 Conclusion**

365 In conclusion, this work analysed an outbreak caused by an X-strain, which successfully persisted
366 for at least 25 years among our population. We were able to discard four cases included by IS6110-
367 RFLP in the Ara50 outbreak that finally were not caused by the Ara50 strain. Besides, it showed TB
368 at its worst, as this strain affected vulnerable people, such as ID users, incarcerated, HIV+ and
369 homeless. The strain did not develop antibiotic resistance, a remarkable fact taking into account the
370 number of relapses and poor adherence to treatment. WGS was useful in the identification of three
371 sub-CLS, one of them with the acquisition of an SNP in a gene considered as a virulence factor.
372 This SNP, together with the 10 SNPs in genes involved in virulence, could explain the successful
373 spread of this strain and its sub-CLS 1 variant, which has co-existed with the Ara50 strain since the
374 beginning of the study in 1993. Finally, although the last registered case was in 2018, we do not
375 rule out the possibility of new cases in the next years, as the strain has demonstrated efficacy in
376 latency.

377

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487 **Author contributions**

488 **Jessica Comín:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing -
489 Review & Editing, Visualization **Alberto Cebollada:** Software, Formal Analysis, Data Curation
490 **Daniel Ibarz:** Investigation **Jesús Viñuelas:** Resources **María Asunción Vitoria:** Resources
491 **María José Iglesias:** Resources **Sofía Samper:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing -
492 Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Strain	Point of insertion	Gene
Ara50	483296	<i>mmpS1</i>
	1979899*	<i>cut1</i>
	3120523-3121879	DR region
	3123104	DR region
	3377327	<i>ppe46</i>
	3665328*	<i>MT3427</i> (extra IS of Case 36)
Non-Ara50 X strain	483296	<i>mmpS1</i>
	888920	<i>Rv0794c:Rv0795</i>
	1979899*	<i>cut1</i>
	3120523-3121879	DR region
	3377327	<i>ppe46</i>
Haarlem 1	483296	<i>mmpS1</i>
	1075948	<i>Rv0963c</i>
	1715972	<i>mmpL12</i>
	1986622	<i>Rv1754c</i>
	1987254	<i>plcD</i>
	2610861	<i>Rv2336</i>
	3120523-3121879	DR region
	3550924	<i>Rv3183</i>
	3668575-3668756*	<i>MT3429</i>
Haarlem 2	79922	<i>Rv0071</i>
	153026	<i>ppe19</i>
	483296	<i>mmpS1</i>
	1075948	<i>Rv0963c</i>
	1986622	<i>Rv1754c</i>
	2038634	<i>Rv1798:lppT</i>
	2610861	<i>Rv2336</i>
	2634049	<i>ppe38</i>
	3076505*	DR region
	3120523-3121879	DR region
	3491619	<i>ppe49</i>
	3668575-3668756*	<i>MT3429</i>

496 **Table 1.** IS6110 location for the Ara50-type, Case 36 (with six bands in the RFLP instead of five)
497 and the outgroup strains (non-Ara50 X strain, Haarlem 1 and Haarlem 2). *Points referred to
498 *M.bovis* genome.

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	N (total N = 56)
Age (years)	
0-15	2
16-30	15
31-45	24
46-60	9
>60	6
HIV state	
HIV+	30
HIV-	24
Unknown	2
Use of Intravenous drugs (ID)	
User or ex-user of (ID)	19
No use of ID	30
Unknown	7
Smoking	
Smoker	33
Non smoker	9
Unknown	14
Alcohol consumption	
High	11
Moderate	7
Low/No consumption	22
Unknown	16
Family structure	
Structured	14
Dysfunctional*	14
Unknown	28
Previous TB contact	
Yes	4
No	37
Unknown	15
Treatment compliance	
Correctly	8
Irregularly/No	10
Unknown	38
Bacilloscopy (BK) result	
BK+	32
BK-	24

505 **Table 2.** Age and risk factors associated with the X-family strain outbreak. *Dysfunctional family
506 structure includes prisoners, indigents and prostitution. The unknown data are not considered in the
507 percentage.

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Case	Gender	Age	Culture date	BK	Country of origin	Comments
Case 3	Female	28	24/05/1993	+	Spain	Treated of TB in 1988. Involved in prostitution.
Case 20	Female	12	09/06/1995	-	Spain	
Case 27	Male	43	18/10/2002	+	Spain	Previous TB episode. Methadone unit.
Case 29	Male	40	07/04/2003	+	Spain	Methadone unit.
Case 32	Male	43	06/09/2003	-	Spain	Methadone unit.
Case 38	Male	39	09/05/2006	+	Spain	Penitentiary
Case 39	Male	46	17/05/2006	+	Spain	Methadone unit. Penitentiary. Indigence.
Case 41	Male	34	11/07/2006	-	Spain	
Case 52	Male	82	27/12/2013	+	Spain	Possible previous TB episode
Case 56	Female	46	05/12/2018	-	Spain	

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511 **Table 3.** Epidemiological information of the isolates involved in the sub-CLS 1.

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532 **Table 4.** SNP distance between different isolates. Shading in blue are the isolates with ≤ 5 SNPs
 533 between them, indicating a recent contact. (This table should be in colour in the printed version).

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Case 30	Case 33	Case 20	Case 27	Case 29	Case 41	Case 52	Case 38	Case 36	Case 36B	Case 14	Case 31	Case 2	Case 17	Case 16	Case 22	Case 37	Case 26	Case 47	Case 30	Case 45	Case 44	Case 46	Case 28	Case 55	Case 50	Case 32	Case 49	Case 34	Case 48	Case 56	Case 43	Case 54	Case 53	
7	7	7	7	7	9	8	10	6	5	4	3	3	3	3	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	7	8	11	0	12	11	13	31	
7	8	8	7	9	10	9	10	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	6	6	6	6	6	7	7	7	7	7	8	10	9	12	10	13	12	7	30
6	6	6	6	8	8	11	10	6	6	5	5	5	5	5	6	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	8	10	9	12	10	13	12	7	30
9	10	10	9	11	11	12	11	7	7	6	6	6	6	6	7	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	9	11	11	14	12	15	14	0	28
9	10	10	9	11	12	11	13	7	7	6	6	6	6	6	7	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	9	11	14	12	15	14	0	28	
4	5	5	4	4	6	7	6	7	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	7	6	9	7	10	9	21	31
3	4	4	3	3	5	6	5	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	4	6	5	8	6	9	8	24	31
3	4	4	3	3	5	6	5	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	4	6	5	8	6	9	8	24	31
3	4	4	3	3	5	6	5	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	4	6	5	8	6	9	8	24	31
5	6	6	5	5	7	8	7	8	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	7	6	9	7	10	9	21	31
5	6	6	5	5	7	8	7	8	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	7	6	9	7	10	9	21	31
5	6	6	5	5	7	8	7	8	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	7	6	9	7	10	9	21	31
6	7	7	6	6	8	9	8	9	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	8	7	10	8	11	10	18	31	
6	7	7	6	6	8	9	8	9	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	8	7	10	8	11	10	18	31	
6	7	7	6	6	8	9	8	9	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	8	7	10	8	11	10	18	31	
6	7	7	6	6	8	9	8	9	4	3	3	3	3	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6	8	7	10	8	11	10	18	31	
7	8	8	7	9	10	9	10	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	6	6	6	6	6	7	7	7	7	7	8	10	9	12	10	13	12	7	30
8	9	9	8	10	11	10	11	6	6	5	5	5	5	5	6	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	8	10	9	12	10	13	12	7	30
11	12	12	11	13	14	13	14	9	9	8	8	8	8	8	9	10	10	10	10	10	11	11	11	11	11	12	14	13	16	14	17	16	0	22
12	13	13	12	14	15	14	15	10	10	9	9	9	9	9	10	11	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12	13	15	14	17	16	17	16	0	22
11	12	12	11	13	14	13	14	9	9	8	8	8	8	8	9	10	10	10	10	10	11	11	11	11	11	12	14	13	16	14	17	16	0	22

Point	Gene	Effect	CLS SNP
4987	<i>Rv0004</i>	Non-synonymous (T185N)	
15198	<i>trpG</i>	Synonymous	
79349	Intergenic region	-	
252810	<i>pckA</i>	Non-synonymous (F343L)	
267176	<i>Rv0223c</i>	Non-synonymous (A197T)	
282798	<i>Rv0236c</i>	Non-synonymous (A1352T)	
408860	<i>Rv0340</i>	Non-synonymous (A76E)	
455794	<i>Rv0378</i>	Non-synonymous (N53T)	
483316	<i>mmpS1</i>	Non-synonymous (C114S)	
559337	<i>fadB2</i>	Non-synonymous (V148G)	
575274	<i>Rv0485</i>	Non-synonymous (D431N)	
581072	<i>regX3</i>	Synonymous	
604044	<i>hemD</i>	Non-synonymous (Q409P)	
625157	<i>fabH</i>	Synonymous	Sub-CLS 2
723561	<i>recB</i>	Non-synonymous (A485S)	
815974	<i>sppA</i>	Synonymous	
884644	<i>Rv0790c</i>	Non-synonymous (R53C)	
1018380	<i>Rv0913c</i>	Non-synonymous (P116T)	
1042060	<i>pstB</i>	Synonymous	
1052125	<i>Rv0941c</i>	Non-synonymous (V65L)	
1072864	<i>Rv0959</i>	Non-synonymous (A537V)	
1114864	<i>Rv0998</i>	Non-synonymous (L39F)	Sub-CLS 3
1300192	Intergenic region	-	
1498542	<i>dinG</i>	Synonymous	Sub-CLS 3
1595376	<i>uvrC</i>	Synonymous	
1670243	<i>moxR1</i>	Non-synonymous (L321V)	
1680504	<i>Rv1490</i>	Synonymous	
1778232	<i>bioD</i>	Non-synonymous (R125H)	
1825730	<i>cydA</i>	Non-synonymous (F53S)	
1825734	<i>cydA</i>	Non-synonymous (K52E)	
1850264	<i>lysX</i>	Non-synonymous (R591L)	
1885648	<i>pks8</i>	Non-synonymous (E1315D)	
2024764	Intergenic region	-	
2095889	<i>Rv1845c</i>	Synonymous	
2212353	<i>mce3C</i>	Non-synonymous (A243V). Virulence factor.	Sub-CLS 1
2277103	<i>Rv2030c</i>	Non-synonymous (F462L)	
2292579	<i>Rv2047c</i>	Non-synonymous (R650C)	Sub-CLS 1
2345187	<i>pknJ</i>	Synonymous	
2362885	<i>helZ</i>	Synonymous	
2580479	<i>Rv2308</i>	Non-synonymous (V21F)	
2637298	Intergenic region	-	
2637385	Intergenic region	-	
2637507	Intergenic region	-	
2692745	Intergenic region	-	
2696235	<i>cysT</i>	Non-synonymous (G138V)	
2698983	<i>Rv2402</i>	Non-synonymous (Y152C)	Sub-CLS 1
2722351	<i>Rv2425c</i>	Non-synonymous (V320L)	
2808813	<i>pdhC</i>	Non-synonymous (M376T)	
2838938	<i>Rv2522c</i>	Non-synonymous (S202G)	

2866569	<i>lppA</i>	Synonymous	
2880258	<i>Rv2560</i>	Non-synonymous (P62S)	
2887762	<i>Rv2566</i>	Non-synonymous (D464H)	
2950970	<i>Rv2624c</i>	Non-synonymous (I113S)	
3076878	Intergenic region	-	
3242032	Intergenic region	-	
3373298	<i>ligA</i>	Synonymous	
3406465	<i>adhC</i>	Non-synonymous (P61A)	
3506567	<i>fadE24</i>	Non-synonymous (G402V)	
3632058	Intergenic region	<i>alkB:Rv3252c</i>	Sub-CLS 2
3641091	<i>fbiA</i>	Synonymous	
3669602	<i>usfY</i>	Non-synonymous (Q133R)	
3698051	<i>sapM</i>	Non-synonymous (G285D)	
3784937	<i>Rv3371</i>	Synonymous	
3806157	<i>acrA1</i>	Synonymous	
3828309	<i>choD</i>	Non-synonymous (R140H)	
3849942	<i>Rv3431c</i>	Synonymous	
4014776	<i>fadE34</i>	Synonymous	
4109100	<i>acs</i>	Non-synonymous (A437P)	
4133100	<i>Rv3691</i>	Non-synonymous (L195I)	
4194065	<i>ctpJ</i>	Non-synonymous (L437F)	Sub-CLS 2
4220833	<i>lipE</i>	Synonymous	
4232392	<i>Rv3785</i>	Non-synonymous (I402M)	
4252725	<i>fadE35</i>	Synonymous	
4255902	<i>accD4</i>	Non-synonymous (A16E)	

535

536 **Table 5.** Location points, gene names and effect of the SNPs used to construct the dendrogram. In
537 the fourth column, the specific SNPs of each sub-CLS are indicated.

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Point	Change	Gene	Mutation effect
108	C/T	<i>dnaA</i>	Synonymous
255919	C/T	<i>Rv0213c</i>	Neutral
284403	G/A	<i>Rv0236c</i>	Neutral
401678	C/A	<i>Rv0336</i>	Neutral
417516	C/T	<i>Rv0347</i>	Synonymous
459674	C/A	<i>clpB</i>	Neutral
559218	G/A	<i>fadB2</i>	Synonymous
597033	C/T	<i>mmpS2</i>	Deleterious
633535	G/C	<i>Rv0541c</i>	Synonymous
647079	C/T	<i>menD</i>	Deleterious
698024	G/A	<i>Rv0600c</i>	Synonymous

731417	G/GT	Intergenic region	-
735645	G/A	<i>rplA</i>	Synonymous
736873	G/T	<i>mmaA4</i>	Neutral
750554	G/A	<i>Rv0654</i>	Synonymous
751114	G/C	<i>Rv0654</i>	Neutral
765756	A/G	<i>rpoC</i>	Neutral
804811	C/T	<i>rpsC</i>	Deleterious
900847	A/C	<i>cpsY</i>	Neutral
916303	G/T	<i>Rv0822c</i>	Neutral
1174496	C/T	<i>Rv1051c</i>	Deleterious
1252229	C/T	<i>Rv1128c</i>	Synonymous
1348388	G/A	<i>Rv1204c</i>	Synonymous
1414145	C/G	<i>pknH</i>	Neutral
1439087	C/A	<i>cysN</i>	Synonymous
1505464	C/T	<i>murI</i>	Synonymous
1639696	C/T	<i>qor</i>	Deleterious
1682091	G/GT	Intergenic region	-
2009062	G/C	<i>Rv1774</i>	Neutral
2117784	C/G	<i>Rv1868</i>	Synonymous
2140945	A/G	<i>Rv1894c</i>	Synonymous
2238104	T/A	Intergenic region	-
2283073	G/T	<i>Rv2037c</i>	Synonymous
2419009	G/T	<i>murE</i>	Neutral
2674765	G/A	<i>mbtB</i>	Deleterious
2696712	C/T	<i>subI</i>	Neutral
2788092	G/A	<i>plsB2</i>	STOP
3011258	G/A	<i>Rv2693c</i>	Synonymous
3161596	G/A	<i>mgo</i>	Neutral
3260089	C/T	<i>ppsC</i>	Synonymous
3285146	C/T	<i>mmpL7</i>	Neutral
3418187	C/G	<i>Rv3057c</i>	Deleterious
3599381	C/A	<i>sigH</i>	Deleterious
3638593	C/T	<i>pmmA</i>	Synonymous
3652581	G/A	<i>ctpC</i>	Deleterious

3684733	C/G	<i>atsB</i>	Deleterious
3785262	T/C	<i>Rv3371</i>	Deleterious
3791079	G/A	<i>Rv3377c</i>	Synonymous
4020500	C/A	<i>arsB2</i>	Deleterious
4047400	T/C	<i>Rv3604c</i>	Deleterious
4163903	C/T	<i>Rv3720</i>	Synonymous
4264301	G/A	<i>Rv3802c</i>	Neutral
4350254	C/T	<i>Rv3871</i>	Synonymous
4356831	A/C	<i>Rv3878</i>	Neutral
4379359	A/G	<i>Rv3894c</i>	Synonymous
4401018	C/G	<i>Rv3912</i>	Deleterious
4403914	G/A	<i>Rv3915</i>	Synonymous

539 **Table S1.** Location points, nucleotide changes, gene names and mutation effects of Ara50 specific
540 SNPs. The points are referred to H37Rv genome.

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554 **Figure captions**

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556 **Fig 1.** A: IS6110-RFLP patterns of the strains selected in the Bionumerics database as possible
 557 evolution of the Ara50 strain. After WGS, we found that Case 36 and Case 36B had an additional
 558 band corresponding to a transposition of IS6110. One selected isolate was an X strain but did not
 559 belong to the Ara50 outbreak, and two isolates were Haarlem strains. The genomic sequence was
 560 not available for Case 53, although it was considered as belonging to the cluster. B: IS6110-RFLP
 561 and Spoligotyping of Ara50 and CDC1551 strains. Four bands in the RFLP are shared by both
 562 strains.

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564 **Fig 2.** Number of cases along the period studied. There was no available data during the period
 565 1996–2000. A reduction in the number of cases during the second period of the study was observed,
 566 so the trend would seem to be the elimination of the strain. A second isolate of Case 36 and non-
 567 Ara50 cases finally excluded by WGS are omitted in the graphic.

568

569 **Fig 3.** Dendrogram based on SNP analysis. The numbers indicate the SNP position relative to the
 570 H37Rv genome. Specific SNPs of sub-CLS 1 are marked in dark red. Specific SNPs of sub-CLS 2
 571 are marked in pink. Specific SNPs of sub-CLS 3 are marked in yellow. (This figure should be in
 572 colour in the printed version).

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577 **Fig 4.** Confirmed, probable and possible links traced using both genomic and epidemiological
 578 information. Letters corresponded to different neighbourhoods of Zaragoza. Within sub-CLS 1, the
 579 ones with the SNP in position 2212353 are coloured in light blue, and the ones without the SNP are
 580 coloured in dark blue. The ones in red are users or ex-users of ID. The ones with the black circles
 581 are the ones sequenced by WGS. Cases without epidemiological or genomic links do not appear in
 582 the diagram. The two cases in sub-CLS3 are not grouped together. (This figure should be in colour
 583 in the printed version).

584

585 **Fig S1.** Phylogenetic tree based on the genomes including CDC1551, Ara50, X non-Ara and
 586 H37Rv strains. X non-Ara50 strain seemed to be more related with CDC1551 than Ara50 strain.
 587 H37Rv appeared as an outgroup.